

The Solubility of Mercuric Bromide in Ethyl and Methyl Alcohols.

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In the course of another piece of work (Dunnicliff and Lal, *Analyst*, 1927, **52**, 329) it was considered necessary to determine the solubility of mercuric bromide in (a) wet alcohol and (b) "absolute" alcohol of a purity such as would be easily attainable. This work was done some time ago (Indian Science Congress, Calcutta, 1928) but in view of the solubility tables given by Lloyd and collaborators (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **133**, 658) it was thought that these values might be of use to other workers.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The recrystallised mercuric bromide (m. p. 242-243°) gave a degree of purity 99.76%.

The alcohols were dried first by standing over anhydrous potassium carbonate and then by repeated redistillation over freshly burnt lime. $D_{40}^{15.0} = 0.7943$ corresponded to 99.78 per cent. ethyl alcohol and that of methyl alcohol = 0.7961 corresponded to 99.88 per cent. alcohol by weight.

The determination of solubility.—Unless otherwise mentioned the solubility determinations were made by Alexeev's synthetic method (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1880, (ii), **39**, 145) in a thermostat controlled electrically to within $\pm 0.05^\circ$.

Solubility in 99.78 per cent Ethyl Alcohol.

Weight of mercuric bromide in gms.	Weight of alcohol in gms.	Temp. °C.	Solubility in 100 gms. of alcohol.
0.8882	3.6949	0.0	24.04*
0.4158	1.5804	16.15	26.25
1.1552	4.0678	24.95	28.40†
1.4800	5.0542	29.15	29.28‡
0.4690	1.5375	31.35	30.05
0.4939	1.5832	34.30	31.29
0.5345	1.5326	41.60	33.53
0.5423	1.5697	44.80	34.55
0.5576	1.5571	48.60	35.87
0.5260	1.5424	58.20	37.80
0.6255	1.5630	58.00	39.80
0.6908	1.5525	60.15	40.63
0.6186	1.4536	64.80	43.10
4.1810	6.7490	79.25	60.15*

Solubility in 87.73 per cent Ethyl Alcohol.

Weight of HgBr ₂ in gms.	Weight of alcohol in gms.	Temp. °C.	Solubility in 100 gms. of alcohol.
0.3121	1.8123	32.90	17.22
0.3914	1.8258	42.13	21.44
0.4082	1.7822	45.20	22.91
0.4446	1.7538	49.07	25.35
0.5198	1.8596	55.85	28.61
0.5438	1.7082	61.60	31.84
0.5230	1.4094	68.97	37.11

Solubility in 99.88 per cent Methyl Alcohol.

(with Karam Chand Taxali)**

Weight of HgBr ₂ in gms.	Weight of alcohol in gms.	Temp. °C.	Solubility in 100 gms. of alcohol.
1.0634	1.5578	22.10	67.62
1.5099	1.5965	27.40	68.81
1.1078	1.8770	30.80	70.25
1.1411	1.5846	36.10	73.31
1.1831	1.4058	49.80	84.43

* By Tschugaeff and Chlopin's method (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1914, 86, 154).

† By direct precipitation as HgS.

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The values are in agreement with the rule of Von Weimarn (*J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, **40**, 1128) that solubilities of salts in methyl alcohol are greater than in ethyl alcohol. The values obtained for the solubility in ethyl alcohol are consistently lower than those recorded by Timofeiew (*Dissertation*, 1894) whose paper is not available for comparison of the method and the strength of alcohol employed. The solubilities in methyl alcohol are higher than those obtained by the same author, but are in fair agreement with those given by Lloyd and others (*loc. cit.*).

On allowing a saturated solution of mercuric bromide in methyl alcohol to stand for a few hours, voluminous needle-like crystals developed in the tube, probably due to the formation of a methyl alcoholate. On analysis of the solid phase at the laboratory temperature, 1.4189 gms. gave Hg=50.86. HgBr₂, CH₃OH requires Hg=51.11 per cent.

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